

Potential of Spaceborne GNSS-R for Land Applications

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ABSTRACT

Recently Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) Reflectometry (GNSS-R) is emerging as an alternative or a complement to classical approaches for Earth remote sensing. GNSS-R techniques can be viewed as a multi-static radar, based on the exploitation of the GNSS signals of opportunity. One of the main advantages that this technique offers, is that with only one passive receiver it is possible to acquire several acquisitions simultaneously, as many as the number of visible GNSS satellites. Initially, GNSS-R was conceived for ocean mesoscale scatterometry and altimetry, but its use has been extended to other fields, such as land applications. Several experiments carried out from aircrafts, towers and balloons, have preliminary demonstrated sensitivity of GNSS-R observations to retrieve land geophysical parameters, such as soil moisture and vegetation biomass.

The European Space Agency is funding a project (ESA/ESTEC CONTRACT n. 4000120299/17/NL/AF/hh) aiming at demonstrating to which extent what we know from models and past ground/airborne experiments on GNSS-R applications for soil moisture and vegetation biomass is: i) still applicable from space, ii) which additional phenomena one should try to model/explain, iii) which final bio-geophysical products one can deliver and how (with recommendations for future systems).

The project involves a large team that is looking at the problem from different perspectives. After the review of the state of the art, TechDemoSat and CYGNSS data have been pre-processed to generate and compare different observables (SNR and surface reflectivity) that have been co-located in space

and time with other sources of soil moisture and biomass data, both at global scale and in specific test areas. We have considered SMAP soil moisture and vegetation optical depth (VOD), SMOS soil moisture (different products having different resolution), as well as in situ soil moisture probe networks. As for biomass, in addition to SMAP VOD we have considered global maps available in the literature, forest height data from spaceborne laser (ICESat), as well as comparison with biomass retrievals from L-band SAR data collected by the ALOS-2 mission over specific sites. Some investigations using airborne GNSS-R data were devoted to understanding the peculiarity of spaceborne data that should be considered to assess their real capability for land applications. For instance, the fluctuations of the signals from different platforms have been compared, and the different behaviours (larger fluctuations of satellite data) have been ascribed to surface inhomogeneity, as well as surface topography and signal coherent/incoherent integration and sampling.

Then, as a first step, the sensitivity of the reflections (including specular coherent reflection and to some extent diffuse incoherent scattering) to soil moisture and forest biomass has been considered and compared to predictions carried out by two different simulators based on rigorous electromagnetic modelling frameworks. A number of updates to the previously developed simulators have been implemented to account for some peculiarities of the satellite case, that poses additional problems due to the low magnitude of the reflected signals and their fluctuations. In particular, we have implemented the effect of topography including a digital elevation model and of the surface inhomogeneity within the discriminated area in both simulators and we have compared their outcomes.

Finally, retrieval approaches have been applied to satellite GNSS-R data to assess the expected accuracy through a comparison with the collocated reference data indicated before. Different approaches have been considered, such as simple multivariate linear regressions or more advanced neural network simulators. It was considered that a single observable from the current GNSS-R mission is not capable to retrieve accurately earth surface parameters due to the complexity of the target (combined effect of moisture, roughness, vegetation) so the algorithms take generally advantage from a multi-sensor approach. For instance, the soil moisture retrieval exploits the knowledge of the vegetation conditions (e.g., through the SMAP VOD or other satellite products), or the biomass retrieval can take advantage from a combination of GNSS-R and L-band SAR data.

At the time of the conference the project will be almost completed so that the presentation will give a review of the most important outcomes.